

NEWSLETTER

RESULTS →

JOINT FLASH

After spotlighting the results of BIMProve in the last Joint Flash edition, the cluster of the four digital building twin projects funded under Horizon 2020 (LC-EEB-08-2020) came up with a new edition on the developments of **COGITO**, **BIM2TWIN** and **ASHVIN**. This fresh edition aims to close this sharing of experiences, knowledge and research outcomes by presenting the results across these three European construction projects.

During three and a half years, the cluster projects have developed novel solutions in digital twins to support the European building and civil engineering sector. And this cluster has enabled the projects so share knowledge and research experiences, establishing synergies to host joint events and create joint publications.

Cluster of Digital Twin projects sharing research experience, knowledge and outcomes.

DIGITAL TWIN TECHNOLOGIES IN THE CONSTRUCTION

Now, these initiatives are finalising their research, and it is time to sum up and showcase the significant technical developments and research results of each ending project that can benefit the entire European construction sector.

Check out the first edition of this newsletter [here](#), where we present each of the four sister projects.

Enjoy your reading!

DIGITAL TWIN

*CO*nstruction phase *di*gItal Twin *m*oDel

TECHNICAL INNOVATION

In alignment with the project objectives, within **COGITO**, a comprehensive set of 14 tools has been developed and delivered to achieve the following aims: timely detection and mitigation of safety hazards to protect workers; swift identification of quality defects; and real-time workflow management on infrastructure construction sites. To ensure seamless integration among the various tools of the COGITO architecture, advanced methods and technologies have been implemented within the Digital Twin platform, which forms the core of this toolset. The COGITO Digital Twins ecosystem relies on harmonised interfaces, standardised data structures, ontologies, communication protocols, and data formats, delivering a reusable and extensible construction digital twin. Detailed documentation for all tools is accessible through the [COGITO community on Zenodo](#). The COGITO toolset has been assessed and has been grouped into the following 4 main technical innovations that have been published in the EU Innovation Radar platform:

- **Innovation 1:** A Cloud-based Digital Twin Platform for nD BIM and IoT Data Management in Planning and Construction Phases Enhanced with an Off-site Data Visualisation Solution;
- **Innovation 2:** A Digital Toolset for Automated Construction Quality Control, supported by an On-site Digital Twin Visualisation with Augmented Reality Solution, to Minimise Project Time and Cost Overruns;
- **Innovation 3:** A Digital Toolset for the Elimination of Construction site Accidents based on Health & Safety Prevention through Design and Planning, Proactive Real-time Risk Monitoring and Detection, and Personalise Safety Education and Learning;
- **Innovation 4:** A Digital Toolset for Trusted, Up-to-date Construction Workflow Management with Integrated Interfaces for Project Managers, Foremen and Workers.

INSIGHTS FROM STAKEHOLDERS

To facilitate an early beta-testing process, the consortium established a school pre-validation pilot, utilising the School sample project provided by Autodesk, tailored to the needs of the COGITO ecosystem. This preliminary testing phase was followed by the release of updated, fully functional versions of all COGITO components that were qualified for pre-validation in actual environments.

Subsequently, the updated versions of the COGITO tools were pre-validated in an actual, medium-scale infrastructure construction site in Karlsruhe, Germany. Engaging with end-users in the field, we gained valuable feedback directly from those who will benefit most from our innovations. Based on this experience, user manuals and supporting documents, including requirements and guidelines, accessible through the [COGITO community on Zenodo](#), have been authored and are continuously updated to facilitate the further deployment of the COGITO toolset and enable its unsupervised utilisation by professionals in the AEC industry.

LAST STEPS

As COGITO approaches its end in April 2023, we're focused on ensuring that the project's impact and legacy endure long into the future.

Currently, we're conducting a thorough evaluation of our pilot results, taking into account local conditions and assessing various factors such as construction process acceleration, collaboration enhancement, worker health and safety, construction quality, and workflow monitoring efficiency. This evaluation will inform further actions and interventions, setting the stage for the successful exploitation of COGITO components to meet real market and industry needs.

Simultaneously, we're in the final stages of crafting our exploitation plan, which will outline strategies for maximising the impact of our project outcomes beyond its conclusion. This plan will pave the way for potential commercialisation of COGITO components, driving adoption within the construction industry and fostering ongoing innovation in digital twin technologies.

Additionally, we're actively promoting our results to standardisation bodies, making significant contributions to technical reports and participating in workshops focused on analysing the standardisation potential and needs in digital twins within the built environment.

Stay updated on our progress and developments by following us on our social media channels ([Website](#), [LinkedIn](#), [X](#), [YouTube](#))

Digitising and transforming the European construction industry

TECHNICAL INNOVATION

The digital **ASHVIN system** includes several technical layers that enable the end-users to collect data from construction sites or infrastructure asset sites, analyse and monitor the collected data, and visualise it through a dedicated digital twin platform. This enables notably better and informed decision-making, risk anticipation and damage detection across construction and maintenance projects.

The figure below shows that the ASHVIN platform integrates sensor devices and edge computing instances to collect data. This data is fed to the ASHVIN system via an Internet of Things platform (IoT) (created and managed by **Mainflux**), allowing connectivity, data management and sensor/edge computing device management. This platform is integrated with the game engine-based digital twin platform (developed by **Digital Twin Technology**) that allows 3D visualisation. In addition, the **ASHVIN toolkit**, composed of 10 digital smart building tools, runs on the Digital Twin platform, enabling it to monitor and assess different aspects of the project based on its needs.

Dive with us into the ASHVIN Digital Twin Platform in our playlist on YouTube [here!](#)

INSIGHTS FROM STAKEHOLDERS

The ASHVIN system was validated at **10 European demonstration** sites from 3 project management phases: design, construction and maintenance. Since last Spring 2023, the ASHVIN project openly invited ongoing construction projects to participate in the demonstration of its digital twin platform. The joint efforts of partners have been effective as **13 new construction sites external to the project onboarded the platform**.

In general, ASHVIN developments have been recognized by both public and private organisations as helpful for various reasons. They help in understanding the building's performance, improving communication streams, providing accessible data that is transparent and transferable, assessing resource utilisation when it comes to designing, and studying multiple layers of information at once through a **user-friendly interface**. However, end-users have suggested the inclusion of tracking critical components of bridges, such as expansion joints, which are the most recurrently damaged part, and integrating contractors in the construction phase.

LAST STEPS

The ASHVIN project is ending in March 2024, and during this month, the **final technical deliverables will be published**. These will share the project's research results and methodologies across the different technical work packages dedicated notably to 4D visualisation concepts, digital twin-based safety management, interoperable digital twin business and the exploitation plans of the system beyond the project's ending.

In addition, as an EU-funded research and innovation action, the **ASHVIN team has published over 19 peer-reviewed scientific papers in conferences and journals**. These are among the key legacies of our research, which benefit our industrial and academic stakeholders and will remain open access beyond the project's lifetime.

Finally, **among the 15 ASHVIN partners, many researchers and experts continue to develop the digital twin technologies and methodologies further** as part of their new commercial and/or research projects, with the aim of making digital twin technologies a routine process supporting the productivity, efficiency, and safety of the construction sector.

Our open digital repository provides all public deliverables and scientific publications [here!](#)

Building a Digital Building Twin platform for construction management to reduce operational waste of all kinds

TECHNICAL INNOVATION

The goal of the **BIM2TWIN** has been to **reduce all kinds of operational waste**, schedule shortenings, cost reductions, quality, safety improvement, and carbon footprint reduction. BIM2TWIN created a **Digital Building Twin platform for construction site management** with artificial intelligence and semantically linked data techniques providing full simulation awareness and extensive construction management applications. The platform provides a **complete situational insight** into the as-built and as-performed processes, which uses and compares to the as-designed applications to implement a close-loop plan-do-check-act process. This entire process relies on multiple onsite sensors for data acquisition, cross-domain analysis, and complex AI-based event processing. The Digital Building Twin offers a **programming interface application** that allows construction management applications to cooperate with its data, information, and knowledge bases.

BIM2TWIN ONLINE WEBINAR SERIES

THE PROJECT

BIM2TWIN is an EU innovation project that creates a Digital Building Twin platform for construction site management with artificial intelligence and semantically linked data techniques. The platform provides a complete situational insight into the as-built and as-performed processes, which uses and compares to the as-designed applications to implement a close-loop plan-do-check-act process. This entire process relies on multiple onsite sensors for data acquisition, cross-domain analysis, and complex AI-based event processing. The Digital Building Twin offers a programming interface application that allows construction management applications to cooperate with its data, information, and knowledge bases.

1 **1st of March 2024 - 11:00-12:00 (CET Time)**
Webinar on the Digital Building Twin Platform

2 **8th of March 2024 - 11:00-12:00 (CET Time)**
Webinar on Progress Monitoring and Quality Control for Volumetric Building, Surface and Textural Work

3 **22nd of March 2024 - 11:00-12:00 (CET Time)**
Webinar on Demonstration Pilots

4 **26th of March 2024 - 12:00-13:00 (CET Time)**
Webinar on Digital Twins for Workers' Occupational Safety & Health and Equipment Optimization

5 **1st of April 2024 - 11:00-12:00 (CET Time)**
Webinar on Production Planning

In March and April, the **BIM2TWIN** project organised a series of **webinars** offering technical and specific insights into the project's different work packages dealing with the Digital Building Twin platform and its applications and its testing on specific demonstration sites where physical building renovation or construction is happening.

1. Digital Building Twin Platform **(1/03/2024)**
2. Progress Monitoring and Quality Control for Volumetric Building, Surface and Textural Work **(8/03/2024)**
3. Demonstration Pilots **(22/03/2024)**
4. Digital Twins for Workers' Occupational Safety & Health and Equipment Optimization **(26/03/2024)**
5. Production Planning **(1/04/2024)**

Register to the upcoming ones [here](#) and watch the recordings session on their YouTube Channel [here!](#)

JOINING FORCES

We are members of the Tech4EUconstruction Cluster. BIM2TWIN has joined the initiative created by the Horizon Europe projects [BEEYONDERS](#), [HumanTech](#), and [RoBétArmé](#): the [Tech4EUconstruction](#) cluster.

The Cluster is open to other EU-funded projects such as BIM2TWIN working on AI and Robotics in Construction, and willing to collaborate on different aspects, such as joint promotional and dissemination activities, mutual exchange of projects' expertise and technical innovations, and co-creation of workshops and events. Funded by the European Commission, the cluster members aim to develop and demonstrate new technologies to digitalise further and automatise the European construction sector, targeting to increase its safety and attractiveness for workers.

Finally, the cluster seeks to stimulate the EU's sovereignty in the industry, decreasing the need for technological imports.

[#Tech4EUconstruction](#)

Welcome to our new partners!

Other projects involved in the cluster are:

- [Humantech](#)
- [Beeyonders](#)
- [Robotarme](#)
- [Reconmatic](#)
- [InCUBE](#)
- [Reincarnate](#)

To be kept up to date on upcoming results and news follow the cluster on social media channels:

- [Linkedin](#)
- [Twitter](#)
- [YouTube](#)

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PROJECTS

UP TO
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MONTHS

53
ENTITIES

1 MISSION

Working for the new wave of a digital European Construction

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